

Academic Problems Faced By Student Teachers of Elementary Education During Practice Teaching Period

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Abstract

During the practice teaching period, it is quite sure that student teachers have to face several work related problems. These problems may be related to school, family support, classroom management, peer involvement, examination and so on. To our understanding, student teachers often face a certain level of academic and non-academic problems as part of the paradigm shift even before they begin their practice teaching. Proper awareness and adequate planning are essential to make the student teachers efficient enough to face and solve those problems. They should be equipped enough through proper coaching even at the beginning of their practice teaching. This study focuses on problems encountered by student teachers of Elementary Education during the practice teaching period and tries to suggest solutions through emerged findings.

Keywords Academic, Problems, Faced, Student Teachers, Elementary, Education, During Practice, Teaching Period.

Introduction

"Teaching might even being the greatest of the arts since the medium is the human mind and spirit".

John Steinbeck

Teaching is a complex activity of both art and science. It is about the human interrelationship which is occurred through sharing of thoughts, content, hearts, minds, ideas and the feature whatever we can image. Teaching and learning are inseparable and are considered as both cases and effects. Practice in teaching is essential for students who are aspiring for teacher profession. Involvement in practice teaching is a requirement as part of the course that is to be taken by the students of education. One of the specific purposes of Practice teaching is to provide experience to students in the real world of teaching and thus give them chances to be teachers at real time situation in school context. Successful practice teaching enable student to enhance their professionalism. It is only through the practice in the real class room situation, the skills in teaching be shaped among student teachers. Thus Practice teaching is one of the crucial components of curriculum which integrates the students in the professional ground of teacher fraternity.

During the practice teaching period, it is quite sure that student teachers have to face several work related problems. These problems may be related to *school, family support, classroom management, peer involvement, examination* and so on. To our understanding, student teachers often face a certain level of academic and non-academic problems as part of the paradigm shift even before they begin their practice teaching. Proper awareness and adequate planning are essential to make the student teachers efficient enough to face and solve those problems. They should be equipped enough through proper coaching even at the beginning of their practice teaching. In Practice teaching, the common academic problems faced by the student teachers are in related to: lesson planning, class management and control, infrastructure and facilities in participating school, method of teaching, ineffective usage of teaching aids, inability to differentiate between the needs of the individual child and supervision, awareness of IT infrastructure and the adequate environmental conditions. To overcome these types of problems during practice teaching, systematic, intelligent and efficient preparation is a must as teachers are made, not born.

If all the preparation and attitude are positively shaped as a passion, everybody can see wonders in their classrooms by experiencing enjoyment and satisfaction through the smiling faces and progress of their students. This study focuses on problems encountered by student teachers of Elementary Education during the practice teaching period and tries to suggest solutions through emerged findings.

Need and Significance of the Study

Teaching as a profession is the noblest one which is having high recognition compared to any other profession. It is obviously a service to human society. It is therefore absolutely necessary for any individuals who want to become a teacher to acquire Attitude, Skills and Knowledge. By acquiring confidence and positive mindset through practice in teaching, students can become the real generation builders and social engineers. Teaching practice is an integral part of teacher education which imparts suitable opportunities to nurture and enhance the capabilities of students in becoming Nation Builders. During the practice teaching phase, there may be various challenges to the teacher trainee due to the new entrance to the academic pursuit. All these challenges and problems are to be captured and recognized so that fruitful solutions can be effected. For the purpose of managing the practice teaching challenges effectively, the teacher trainee has to implement and apply the skills and knowledge he has learnt in the training context. Practice under the supervision of an experienced teacher will help them a lot.

In the field of teacher education, teacher students face problems such as *stress and anxiety, class management problems, over load of academic work, lack of co-operation from the subject teacher, lack of instructional materials, expenses to prepare teaching learning materials, conveyance & transport related issues and resources in schools*. During practice teaching period, usually, students get much work load or responsibility in schools. Another problem is the difficulty in managing students with different skills & poor learning background environment and overcrowded class rooms etc. In addition to purpose of assessment in teaching expertise of the trainee through observation, relevance and purpose of the teaching practice exercise in teacher preparatory programme, a number of challenges appear to hamper the optimum realization of its objectives in the professional growth of students in training. Many student teachers get anxious about extending the class room to taken up teaching tasks in unfamiliar environment. In the day to day life, we do come across to see those types of problems among student teachers. Hence focus of this study is to investigate the various academic challenges faced by student teachers during practice teaching exercise and hence take necessary requirements at the teacher preparatory stage itself. The student teachers are properly trained and made aware to realize the importance of the practice teaching initiative and the allied challenges he/she might face during the period. As a result, the student teacher will get himself/herself ready for facing any of such challenges. Also, the practicing school management should be aware that student teachers are facing challenges during their teaching practice exercise. The practicing school management will be ready to give maximum assistance and co-operation to student teachers. Based on this, the practicing school will equally benefit from the service rendered by the trainees.

It is expected that the results of the study will make the policy makers, curriculum developers, and administrators in the field of teacher education to see the need for an improvement in teaching practice exercise and the entire teacher education programme in general. The result of the study is also expected to take necessary teacher preparatory initiatives, especially during practice teaching by implementing proper arrangements both in the parent institution and practice teaching schools so that the student teacher can work in a productive manner beneficial to the students and school and ultimately to the society. Thus make the teaching profession highly respectable, productive, value embedded and divine.

Research Questions

1. Whether elementary school student teachers face any academic problems during their practice teaching period?
2. Can they themselves solve the particular problem, if any?
3. How can Teacher Educators and School Authorities support student teachers to solve the academic problems which they face during their practice teaching period?

Aim of study

1. To Study the Academic Problems faced by Student Teachers of Elementary Education during Practice Teaching Period

2. To compare the class room management related problems faced by elementary student teachers during their practice teaching period with regard to Rural vs Urban schools.
3. To compare the school related problems faced by elementary student teachers during practice teaching period with regard to Govt. vs Aided schools.
4. To compare the family support related problems of student teachers during practice teaching period with regard to Married vs Unmarried students.
5. To compare the peer support related problems faced by elementary student teachers during practice teaching period with regard to Male vs Female.
6. To compare the exam related problems faced by elementary student teachers during practice teaching period with regard to Male vs Female.

Review of Literature

Ball and Frozani (2009) highlighted teacher educators should prioritize the clinical as part of teaching. To make practice the core of the curriculum of teacher education requires a shift from a focus on what teachers know and believe to greater focus on what teachers do (p.503). In this scenario, Grossman et al (2009) pointed out that, empirical evidence is needed to fully understand how access to various aspects and types of practice both support and hamper the development of student teachers about their teaching skills. Teaching being a skill cannot be taught merely through training during teacher education courses. It only equips student teachers to build knowledge and sketch school class room teaching environment theoretically.

The central thrust of reforms in the teacher education programme is to produce teachers who can perform adequately in the world of work and meet the present day challenges. Teaching practice is a vital aspect of the teacher preparatory programme in teacher training institutions and in Faculties of education. It serves us an opportunity for student – teachers' vis-a-viz supervisors to be exposed to the realities of teaching and professional activities in the field of education. Every profession has its own practical side. The training lawyers, doctors, engineers and other well-known professions make adequate provision for practical work which forms an integral part of the total training of the professions, hence the teaching practice exercise is the practical aspect of the teacher education programme. A sound profession and teaching practice constitutes an important and indispensable component of the process involved in the adequate preparation of professional teachers.

According to Adesina et al., (1989) teaching practice can be defined as a teacher education programme or activity which involves the student teacher putting in to practice his/her acquired theory of teaching under the genuine experience of the normal classroom situation. It is an opportunity for student-teachers to face the realities of their chosen careers in terms of its demands, challenges and excitement. It can also be seen as the periods when student teachers are aided to put in to practice the theories and principles of education which they have learnt in the classroom as they teach.

Practice teaching is an important component towards becoming a teacher. It provides experiences to student teachers in the actual teaching and learning environment. During teaching practice a student teacher is given the opportunity to try the art of teaching before actually getting in to the real world of the teaching profession. Student teachers also know the value of teaching practice and they perceive it as the important aspect of their preparation for the teaching profession since it provides for the real interface between student hood and membership of the profession (Rakesh Ranjan, 2013).

The frame work for teacher education proposes the preparation process of teachers be done in such a way that it reflects the paradigm shift from the content-based to competency based approach in teaching and learning (TIE, 2009). Schultz (2005) provides support for the concept of day-to-day problem solving capacity development through practicum learning. The study highlighted the need for teacher preparation to support new teacher inquiry to help teacher candidates use problem solving approaches when they face the day-to-day challenges in a class room. A study by Brouwer & Korthagen (2005) confirmed the roll of the practicum in the overall development of competent teachers. While both class room theory and practicum experiences were found to be contributors to a new teacher's development, the practicum in a school context was more influential than the course component of the teacher education program on the development of teaching competence.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. Elementary school student teachers face class room management related problems during their practice teaching period
2. Elementary school students do face school related problems during the practice teaching period
3. Elementary school students do face family support related problems during the practice teaching
4. Elementary school student teachers face peer related problems during their practice teaching period
5. Elementary School Student teachers face examinations related problems, during their practice teaching period

Methodology

1. Research method adopted for the study

Survey method was adopted for the collection of data for the study

2. Population of study

Elementary Education students of Kerala State

Sampling

300 student teachers of Elementary Education of the years of duration from 2017-2021

Tools Used

Questionnaire on Academic Problems of Elementary Education students with due emphasis on

1. Class room management related problems
2. School related problems
3. Family support related problems
4. Peer group related problems
5. Examination related problems

faced by the student teachers during practice teaching period. The questionnaire contains 30 items of yes/no type questions of six each from the select 5 categories.

Analysis

Procedure of data collection

First of all, the investigator prepared a tool for the purpose of collecting data, a questionnaire. After consultation with the experts and supervising teacher, a final tool was prepared. The final prepared tool was distributed to the sample for collecting data. The filled questionnaires were collected back from the sample for further data analysis.

Statistical technique applied for the data analysis

For analysis of data, percentage analysis and Test of significance of difference between Means were used.

Result and Discussion

Comparison of selected Dimensions of Problems Faced by Student Teachers of Elementary Education during Practice Teaching Period Categorywise

Table No. 1

't'- values for Mean Scores of Dimensions of Problems Faced by Student Teachers of Elementary Education during Practice Teaching Period Category wise.

Variables	Group	N	Mean	SD's	t-values
Class room management related problems	Urban Schools	5	15.67	1.479	3.011*
	Rural Schools	5	17.51	2.871	

School related problems	Govt. Schools	4	15.42	3.67	2.781*
	Aided Schools	6	14.37	2.86	
Examination related problems	Male	68	12.83	2.64	1.758(NS)
	Female	232	12.69	2.62	
Peer group related problems	Male	68	15.73	0.85	1.003(NS)
	Female	232	15.68	0.82	
Family support related problems	Married Trainees &	104	15.01	1.93	4.021*
	Unmarried	196	12.37	1.08	

An examination of Table- 1 reveals that while considering the Class room management related problems, in comparison to Urban Schools(5) and Rural Schools(5), they differ significantly at 0.01 level ($t = 3.011$) and hence the rejection of null hypothesis and which can be interpreted that the student teachers experience more (Mean=17.51) class room related problems in rural schools. Also Infrastructural and school related problems are there ($t = 2.781$) and they are comparatively higher in Government schools(Mean=15.42). While comparing the Family support related problems of Married and Unmarried students, they differ significantly at 0.01 level ($t = 4.021$) and further analysis show that married students do face more family support related problems(Mean=15.01). Examination related problems and Peer group related problems in comparison of male and female do not differ significantly at 0.01 level ($t = 1.758$, $t = 1.003$ respectively).

Findings related to classroom management problems of DI. Ed. student teachers

Table 5.1

Class room management related problems faced by elementary student teachers during their practice teaching period

SI No	Statements	Responses of student teachers			
		Yes		No	
		Number	%	Number	%
1.	Successfully managed the students during the class.	205	68.33	95	31.67
2.	Fruitfully cleared the doubts of students during the class	260	86.67	40	13.33
3.	Difficulties faced while teaching in primary class.	232	77.33	68	22.67
4.	Note books were corrected in a timely manner during the break time of content delivery in the class.	206	68.67	94	31.33
5.	Received any kind of training in teaching children with disabilities.	65	21.67	235	78.33
6.	Experienced difficulties related to English language during teaching practice	230	76.67	70	23.33

1. It is found that 68.33% DI. Ed. student teachers successfully managed the students during their class where as 31.67% student teachers were not able to manage the students during their class.
2. The study revealed that 13.33% student teachers were not able to clear the doubts of students during the class.
3. Majority (77.33%) of student teachers faced difficulties while teaching in primary class
4. Further it is found from the study that 31.33% student teachers were not able to correct the note book of students in a timely manner during the break time of content delivery in the class.
5. Majority (78.33%) of student teachers were not received any kind of training in teaching children with disabilities
6. It is also found that majority of student teachers (76.67%) experienced difficulties related to English language during teaching practice.

Findings on school related problems of DI. Ed. student teachers

Table 5.3

School related problems faced by elementary student teachers during their practice teaching period .

SI No	Statements	Responses of student teachers			
		Yes		No	
		Number	%	Number	%
1.	Assistance was received from the teachers of the practice teaching school.	296	98.67	4	1.33
2.	Faced difficulties from the school authorities during the training.	38	12.67	262	87.33
3.	The lab, library and ICT facilities of the selected school could be utilized properly during practice teaching	164	54.67	136	45.33
4.	Received the support of the mentor teacher during the training period.	282	94.00	18	6.00
5.	The timetable at practicing school during the training made difficulties.	54	18.00	246	82.00
6.	Necessary facilities and cooperation available for conducting sports activities	190	63.33	110	36.67

1.A vast majority of student teachers (98.67%) responded that assistance was received from the teachers of the practice teaching school where as a negligible per cent (1.33%) student teachers were not received assistance from the teachers of the practice teaching school.

2.The study makes clear that 12.67% student teachers faced difficulties from the school authorities during the training.

3. Further the study revealed that 45.33% student teachers were not able to utilize the lab, library and ICT facilities of the selected school properly during practice teaching.

4. A vast majority (94%) of student teachers received the support of the mentor teacher during the training period whereas 4% of student teachers didn't received the support of the mentor teacher during the training period.

5. It is found that 18.00% student teachers experienced difficulties related to the timetable at practicing school during the training.

6. The study also revealed that 36.67% student teachers reported that necessary facilities and cooperation were not available for conducting sports activities.

Findings on family support related problems of DI. Ed. student teachers

Table 5.5

Family support related problems faced by elementary student teachers during their practice teaching period.

SI No	Statements	Responses of student teachers			
		Yes		No	
		Number	%	Number	%
1.	Experienced financial difficulties during teacher training.	80	26.67	220	73.33
2.	Experienced family related problems that caused the regularity in attending schools.	40	13.33	260	86.67
3.	Complete Parental support received.	300	100.00	0	0.00
4.	Faced difficulties with House hold works during teacher training	100	33.33	200	66.67
5.	Faced Family issues which adversely affected teacher training	70	23.33	230	76.67

1. It is found from the study that 26.67 per cent student teachers experienced financial difficulties during teacher training.

2. The study makes clear that 13.33% student teachers had family related problems which caused difficulty to attend the school regularly.

3. Further the study revealed that 100% student teachers responded that they received complete parental support during practice teaching period.

4. It is found from the study that 33.33% of student teachers faced difficulties with house hold works during teacher training.

5. The study revealed that 23.33% student teachers reported that family issues adversely affected teacher training.

6.The study also revealed that 29.33% student teachers reported that stress experienced during teacher training affected their family life.

Findings based on peer related problems during their practice teaching period

Table 5.7

Peer related problems faced by elementary student teachers during their practice teaching period

Sl No	Statements	Responses of student teachers			
		Yes		No	
		Number	%	Number	%
1.	Received support from fellow students in learning activities during teaching practice.	295	98.33	5	1.67
2.	Received support and suggestions from Fellow students at SRG meeting.	262	87.33	38	12.67
3.	Received help of fellow learners in the preparation of learning materials during the training.	260	86.67	40	13.33
4.	Faced bad experiences from class mates during practice teaching.	32	10.67	268	89.33
5.	Groups of student teachers were formed during teacher training	44	14.67	256	85.33
6.	Experienced difficulties from seniors during teacher training	22	7.33	278	92.67

1.It is found from the study that only negligible per cent (1.63%) student teachers didn't received assistance from fellow students in learning activities during teaching practice.

2.The study revealed that 12.67% student teachers didn't received support and suggestions from fellow students at SRG meeting.

3.Further the study revealed that 13.33% student teachers did not received help of fellow learners in the preparation of learning materials during the training.

4.It is found that only 10.67% of student teachers had bad experiences from class mates during practice teaching.

5.It is found that 14.67% student teachers were not formed any group during teacher training.

6.The study also revealed that 7.33% student teachers experienced difficulties from seniors during teacher training

Findings based on examination related problems during their practice teaching period

1.It is found that 13.64 per cent student teachers were not able to conduct unit test at intervals during teacher training.

2.The study also makes clear that 51.67% student teachers experienced difficulties while preparing unit test items

3.Further the study revealed that 13.33% student teachers were not able to evaluate the answer sheets of unit tests in a timely manner during practice teaching.

4.The findings showed that 11.67% of student teachers didn't use evaluation tools while conducting evaluation during practice teaching.

5.It is found from the study that 12.67% student teachers experienced difficulties through the interference from mentor while conducting unit tests.

6.The study also revealed that 58% student teachers didn't get opportunities to speak at the PTA meeting about the learning level of the children.

Interpretation of Results

From the findings of the study, it is clear that DI. Ed. student teachers faced academic problems related to class room management, school, family support, peer group and examination. Majority of student teachers faced difficulties while teaching in primary class and were not received any kind of training in teaching children with disabilities. More over majority of student teachers experienced difficulties related to English language during teaching practice. One of the chief defects of the present system of education is that the talents of the individuals are not being properly harnessed as education is not according to the aptitude, ability and interest of an individual. The teachers are made to read subjects without reference to any goal. Many teachers fail to understand the subject properly.

More than thirty per cent of student teachers were not able to manage the students during their class and were not able to correct the note book of students in a timely manner during the break time of content delivery in the class. . This may be due to poor class room management skill and lack of knowledge on English language among student teachers. Findings related to class room management problems show the need for providing training in classroom management especially managing children with disabilities.

From the study, it is found that during the practice teaching period some of the student teachers were not able to utilize the lab, library and ICT facilities of the selected school properly during practice teaching and faced difficulties from the school authorities during the training. More than thirty five per cent student teachers reported that necessary facilities and cooperation were not available for conducting sports activities. Some of the student teachers experienced difficulties related to the timetable at practicing school during the training. Only small per cent student teachers were not received assistance from the teachers of the practice teaching school and didn't receive the support of the mentor teacher during the training period. This finding shows the need for making concerned authorities of the school to take necessary steps to provide adequate facilities and attention to student teachers during practice teaching period.

Regarding the family support related problems faced by student teachers during the practice teaching period, some of the student teachers experienced financial difficulties during teacher training and faced difficulties with house hold works during teacher training. Moreover some of the student teachers were not able to attend the school regularly, family issues adversely affected teacher training and they experienced stress during teacher training. But all the teachers received complete parental support during practice teaching period. These findings showed that married woman student teachers experienced problems related to family support. It is the duty of the family members to give care on the education of student teachers.

Some of the student teachers didn't receive support and suggestions from fellow students at SRG meeting and had bad experiences from class mates during practice teaching. Group formation is becoming very common among student teachers during teaching practicing and some of the seniors are providing bad experiences to juniors. This finding depicts the need for making aware of the teacher educators and Principals of the institution to take special care in avoiding such incidents.

Findings based on examination related problems during their practice teaching period showed that some of the student teachers were not able to conduct unit test at intervals during teacher training. More than half of the respondents experienced

difficulties while preparing unit test items, were not able to evaluate the answer sheets of unit tests in a timely manner during practice teaching and experienced difficulties through the interference from mentor while conducting unit tests. Some of the student teachers didn't get opportunities to speak at the PTA meeting about the learning level of the children and were not able to use evaluation tools while conducting evaluation during practice teaching. This may be due to lack of proper understanding regarding the different aspects of evaluation and preparation of evaluation tools for students. Hence adequate training regarding the preparation and use of evaluation tools should be given to teacher trainees before they went for teaching practice.

Implications of the Study

The present study revealed that DI.Ed student teachers faced academic problems related to class room management, school, family support, peer group and examination. From the findings of the study, following implications are proposed by the researcher.

The main purpose of teacher training is to develop better future teachers. The adequate education makes good quality human resources for a rapidly developing country. According to this reason, many countries have been trying to develop the educational quality in the national policy and strategy to enhance effective implementation of school education by various ways in changing the curriculum accordingly. The new teacher education curriculum framework will need to integrate these perspectives in its formulation.

The student teachers at elementary level face many academic problems. The student teachers should be provided with stimulating and encouraging atmosphere at home, school and society for their better academic performance and becoming a best teacher in future life. Principal and teacher educators of the teacher training institution and parents should pay special attention in providing a healthy and friendly atmosphere at school and home so that student teacher can share their problems with them. It is the essential duty of the teachers and school administration to provide good and comfortable environment in school for the student teachers during teaching practice period. School authorities and teachers should provide time for guidance and training to student teachers and help them in solving their problems during teaching practice. Teachers should build a proper and conducive environment. A positive atmosphere in the school will bring about a positive vibe among the student teachers.

Parents should also encourage them to become best teacher. They should guide and motivate them in achieving their goals. Educated parents can provide better guidance as they are aware of the new development in the field of education and help them in achieving their goals. Love and affection and support from parents are the basic psychological needs of everyone that would make him feel secure and thus develop self-confidence. This may give him the necessary courage to enter in to better relationship with peers and develop in them a positive attitude towards life and other people which will enhance their achievement in life.

The teaching learning situation in the classroom should be more of student centred. Training regarding classroom management, school administration and student evaluation. Motivation is an important key needed by the Principal and teacher educators to encourage the student teachers to perform higher in their performances. Any kind of de-motivation from may result as a hindrance in their progress. The following recommendations are made by the investigator to reduce academic problems of student teachers.

Recommendations

In many circumstances, student teachers face academic problem. In solving these academic problems, the educational guidance service acts as light in the darkness and saves many creative lives from destruction. The following approaches are useful for solving the academic problems of student teachers:

- i. Encourage student teachers to improve their classroom management skills.
- ii. Introduce teacher empowerment programmes for student teachers at all levels of teaching.
- iii. Strict supervision is needed during teaching for the development of competent student teachers.

- iv. Special training programmes should be organized to improve the classroom management of student teachers
- v. Micro teaching practice should be executed for as much as teaching skills by following the exact procedure, which may help to develop the required skills for teaching and thus promote and classroom management and evaluation.
- vi. Group activities and team activities must be encouraged among student teachers
- vii. By providing democratic atmosphere in home, school and society by the parents, teacher educators and friend will helps to reduce the academic problems and to improve the mental health of student teachers.
- viii. Counselling may be provided to solve economic, academic, physical, social and psychological problems of the student teachers so that they will be in a position to overcome the problems and develop efficient prospective teachers.
- ix. Student teachers should be guided properly to be independent and to tolerate criticism, disappointment and rejection.
- x. When student teachers experience conflict, they should be guided not to approach any goal hurriedly. They should insist on examining all the alternatives more rationally until they are able to reach an acceptable decision.
- xi. Student teachers should be helped to learn to increase their tolerance for problems.
- xii. Efforts should be made to give the knowledge of the importance of feelings related aspects as well as reasoning, problem solving, etc. from the source of school and school related activities.
- xiii. Student teachers should be helped to understand themselves and their abilities. They should learn from the experience and try to improve the skill needed for success.
- xiv. Proper interaction and relationship should be maintained between teacher educator and student teacher so that a teacher educator can understand his student teachers in a better way to find out the cause of problems. The teacher educator can try to remove/minimize their problems.
- xv. Student teachers should be helped to develop their ability to function while feeling anxious. Most anxious moments pass away when student teachers learn to relax naturally, shifting attention away from the surroundings and adopting a positive attitude towards distracting thoughts.
- xvi. Student teachers should be guided properly to take help form guidance and counseling calls on their future career to reduce the problems. Some bold decisions need to be taken to create problem-free learning by adopting a positive attitude.
- xvii. Teachers of the schools can be given training about dealing effectively with the student teachers pertaining to their academic problem and helping them positively.
- xviii. The student teachers should be helped to adopt positive approach to cope with problems whenever there is a reasonable possibility of success by thinking of various possible solutions to the problem before acting on a solution, sharing one's problems with others, seeking support from others and clearly speaking about the problem with the teacher.
- xix. Give recognition, approval, and stimulates to increase the effort and widen the interest of student teachers.
- xx. Special training should be given to tackle specific learning problems of disabled students like children with mild-disabilities like lower level of intellectual functioning, children with visual impairment, children with hearing-impairment and children with locomotive impairment

xxi. There is a great need to guide the student teachers in preparing their study schedules, proper planning and keep attention focused on the job at hand

xxii. Family members should provide proper support and much attention to the needs and requirements of the student teacher.

Conclusion

The perception voiced by the student teacher regarding their teaching practice experience indicated that the program has some deficiencies that make the experience stress full. Issues related to inadequacy of budget allocated for the students during the Teaching Practice, assessment problems, inadequate support and elementary school students' disciplinary problems emerged as themes from student teachers' response. It is clear that student teachers' practical experience is vital to the preparation of qualified teachers. The effectiveness of the Teaching Practice program is highly linked to its quality components. Therefore, it is imperative that the concerned body is must to ensure the quality of teaching practice so that the students can find it educative and supportive. However, to the contrary findings revealed that program has deficiencies that put question marks on the quality of school based practical experience of student teachers. The insightful response of student teachers about their practicum experiences are very much important and must be acted up on to make the experience fulfilling and satisfying.

Teaching practice program has a lot of challenges that create a negative impact on the time management of the program and on the academic knowledge of the student teacher. In the field of teacher education, teacher students face many problems these are stress and anxiety, class management problems, over load of academic work, lack of finance etc.

This study indicates that student teachers faced a lot of challenges during their teaching practice programme. Majority of the perceived challenges identified in this study were ranked by student teachers as major challenges. However the study revealed that all problems were influenced on perceived challenges faced by student teachers.

Suggestions for the future Study In the light of the present investigation and findings the following suggestions are given by the investigator for the benefit of the future researchers:

1. An experimental study concerned with the preparation of a training module to tackle the academic problems of teachers at primary, secondary, higher secondary and college level can be done.
2. A correlational study on academic problems academic performance of teachers at different levels of learning can be made
3. Academic problems of student teachers can be studied in relation with School environment.
4. Academic problems of student teachers can be studied in relation with Job satisfaction
5. An intensive study can be conducted on competency of student teachers to tackle academic problems.
6. A comparative study can be conducted on the academic problems of various professionals such as teachers, IT professionals, and various officers.
7. A similar study can be taken on academic problems of student teachers at B.Ed and ,M.Ed levels.

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